

ISic3185

I.Sicily inscription 3185

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329579

1. Εὐστάχις ἢ κὲ | Βῶ | κυς
2. ἐκοιμήθη
3. εἰδοῖς Μαίεις ²⁶Μαΐαις²⁶
4. σώφρων καὶ ἀκα-
5. τάνωστος· ἔζησεν
6. ἔτη λε΄
7. καὶ ἀνεπαύσατο.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645515

PHI 329579

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0012

Orsi, P. 1923. Manipulus epigraphicus christianus memoriae aeternae I.B. de Rossi dicatus. Contributi alla Siracusa sotterranea. *Atti della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia. Memorie*. 1: 113-122. At no.11

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.273

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